

Harmonics Elimination in Power Generation Using Active Power Filter

Srinivasa Acharya¹, A. Srihari², A. Bharadwaj manikanta³, T. Sai gowtham⁴, C. Jagadeesh⁵, K. Tanuj⁶
^{1,2,3,4,5,6} *Aditya institute of technology and management, Tekkali*

Abstract- In distribution systems, the load has been a sudden increase or decreases and it is like as nonlinear loads so the load draw non-sinusoidal currents from the AC mains and causes the load harmonics and reactive power, and excessive neutral currents that give pollution in power systems. Most pollution problems created in power systems are due to the nonlinear characteristics and fast switching of power electronic devices. Shunt active filter based on current controlled PWM converters are seen as a most viable solution. This paper presents the harmonics and reactive power compensation from 3P4W micro-grid distribution system by IP controlled shunt active. The technique which is used for generate desired compensation current extraction based on offset command instantaneous currents distorted or voltage signals in the time domain because compensation time domain response is quick, easy implementation and lower computational load compared to the frequency domain.

Index terms- micro grid, level inverters, renewable energy sources

I.INTRODUCTION

Renewable generation affects power quality due to its nonlinearity, since solar generation plants and wind power generators must be connected to the grid through high-power static PWM converters [1]. The non-uniform nature of power generation directly affects voltage regulation and creates voltage distortion in power systems. This new scenario in power distribution systems will require more sophisticated compensation techniques. Although active power filters implemented with three-phase four-leg voltage-source inverters (4L-VSI) have already been presented in the technical literature [2]–[6], the primary contribution of this paper is a predictive control algorithm designed and implemented specifically for this application. Traditionally, active power filters have been controlled using pre tuned controllers, such as PI-type or adaptive, for the current as well as for the dc-

voltage loops [7], [8]. PI controllers must be designed based on the equivalent linear model, while predictive controllers use the nonlinear model, which is closer to real operating conditions. An accurate model obtained using predictive controllers improves the performance of the active power filter, especially during transient operating conditions, because it can quickly follow the current-reference signal while maintaining a constant dc-voltage. So far, implementations of predictive control in power converters have been used mainly in induction motor drives [9]–[16].

In the case of motor drive applications, predictive control represents a very intuitive control scheme that handles multivariable characteristics, simplifies the treatment of dead-time compensations, and permits pulse-width modulator replacement. However, these kinds of applications present disadvantages related to oscillations and instability created from unknown load parameters [15]. One advantage of the proposed algorithm is that it fits well in active power filter applications, since the power converter output parameters are well known [17]. These output parameters are obtained from the converter output ripple filter and the power system equivalent impedance. The converter output ripple filter is part of the active power filter design and the power system impedance is obtained from well-known standard procedures [18], [19]. In the case of unknown system impedance parameters, an estimation method can be used to derive an accurate R–L equivalent impedance model of the system [20]. This paper presents the mathematical model of the 4L-VSI and the principles of operation of the proposed predictive control scheme, including the design procedure. The complete description of the selected current reference generator implemented in the active power filter is also presented. Finally, the proposed active power filter and the effectiveness of